

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES FOR SKIN BIOPSY SAMPLING, PROCESSING, AND IMMUNOSTAINING

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PUNCH BIOPSY SAMPLING:

Setting:	Clinical procedure room		
Tools	Instruments	Reagents	Equipment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-sterile nitrile gloves • Cotton pads • Sterile gloves • 1 mL syringe • 30G hypodermic needle • Elastomull • Micropore 3M • Sterile gauzes • 1.5 ml Eppendorf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 mm diameter punch • Sterile tweezers • Sterile scalpel blade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paraformaldehyde 4% in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) 1X • Ethanol 70% • Lidocaine 2% • WoundSeal powder* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refrigerator (4°C)

*For subjects with inflammatory skin conditions or excessive bleeding.

- Ensure the participant signs the written consent form related to sampling of skin biopsies. Ask the participant for latex, nitrile or lidocaine allergy.

- Prepare a Eppendorf tube with 1.5 ml of PFA 4%. Write the assigned ID and current date on the above surface of the Eppendorf. All the additional information (name, surname, birth date, skin site of sampling its recorded on the clinical record of each subject).

- Instruct the patient to lie on their contralateral side if sampling, for example, if the sample is in the right leg, the patient lies on the left side (or vice versa).

- Mark the selected areas for skin biopsy (10 cm above the lateral malleolus).

- Using non-sterile gloves, cleanse the selected area at least three times with Ethanol solution, disinfecting a circular area of at least 15 cm in diameter around the sampling point.

- Inject subcutaneously 0.5-0.8 ml of lidocaine 2% into the center of the selected area using an hypodermic needle.

- Prepare sterile instruments and tools (gloves, tweezers, scalpel blade, punch, gauzes).

- Around 3 minutes after injection, test pinprick sensitivity using the sterile syringe tip. Proceed with sampling if the patient reports loss of sensation or tactile sensation upon pricking. If pinprick sensitivity persists, recheck after one minute. If sensitivity remains, administer additional 0.2 ml of lidocaine and repeat the sensitivity check.

- Once pinprick sensitivity is locally lost, proceed with sampling using sterile instruments and tools. Position the sterile 3 mm punch over the desired sampling point and gently but firmly push it into the skin using a rotating motion.

- Extract the punch from the skin by handling the sample with the tweezers and the scalpel blade. Immerse the sample in the Eppendorf containing PFA 4%.

- Apply pressure to the sampled area with a sterile gauze for three minutes to control bleeding. Cover the area with a gauzes and fix it with the Elastomull and Micropore 3M.

SKIN BIOPSY PROCESSING, CUT, AND STORAGE:

Setting:	Neuropathic Pain Laboratory		
Tools	Instruments	Reagents	Equipment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-sterile nitrile gloves • 1.5 ml Eppendorf • Disposable 24-well plate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tweezers • Fine tip brush 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phosphate-buffered saline 1X • Sucrose • Sodium azide • OCT Compound 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refrigerator (4°) • Freezer (-20°c) • Cryostat

- Place the biopsy in PFA 4% fixative solution and keep it at room temperature for 2-3 hours.

- Transfer the skin biopsy to a 1.5 mL Eppendorf tube filled with Sucrose 30% + 0.1% Azide using tweezers. Store the sample at 4°C in the refrigerator for 2-3 days.

- Dry the skin biopsy and cover it in OCT at room temperature conditions. Snap-freeze the samples using dry ice or liquid nitrogen. Transfer the sample to -20°C for cryoprotection until cutting.

- Position the sample on a cryostat support and place it in the cryostat. Once frozen, begin cutting with a thickness setting of 50 µM.

- Meanwhile, prepare a 24-well plate filled with PBS 1X and label the lid with the ID of each sample.

- Place each cut skin section into the corresponding well of each sample using a cold fine tip brush. Consider obtaining 5 slices per sample. Each well can contain a maximum of 5 free-floating sections, all from the same sample/subject. Start the immunostaining on the same day (DAY 1) and use the sample 24-well plate.

SKIN SECTIONS FREE-FLOATING IMMUNOSTAINING WITH INDIRECT IMMUNOFLUORESCENCE:

Indirect immunofluorescence staining protocol for PGP9.5 for marking intraepidermal and dermal nerve fibers. Consider using a second antibody and double staining protocol according to your objectives (NF200, MBP, IB4, CGRP, CDK5, P35, among others).

Setting:	Neuropathic Pain Laboratory		
Tools	Instruments	Reagents	Equipment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-sterile nitrile gloves • Adhesive tape • Indelible marker • Disposable 24-wells plates • Pasteur's pipette • Cover slides • Object slides • Pipette • Aluminum foil • Absorbent paper 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipettes (P1000) • Pipettes tips 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phosphate-buffered saline 1X • Block solution • Wash solution • Primary and Secondary antibodies • Fluorescence mounting medium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shaker

DAY 1

- Remove the PBS from each well using a Pasteur's pipette, avoiding touching the floating sections. Immediately add 400 uL of Blocking solution into each well. Block for 1 hour at room temperature with agitation. Refrigerate the plate at 4°C overnight.

DAY 2

- Remove the antibody solution and wash each well 3 times for 45 min with agitation at room temperature using the wash solution.

-After the third wash, dispense 200-300 uL of the solution with the secondary antibodies into each well. Wrap the plate with aluminum foil (secondary antibodies bind fluorescent molecules) and refrigerate it at 4°C overnight.

DAY 3

- Remove the secondary antibody solution and wash each well 3 times for 30 min with agitation at room temperature using the wash solution. Always ensure to rewrap the plates in aluminum foil after each step.

-Remove the wash solution and dispense 1 ml of PBS 1X into each well.

- Prepare one slide for each subject. Write the participant ID, date, and researcher initial.

- Using a Pasteur's pipette, transfer the section onto the slide, avoiding taking too much liquid, and deposit the slides into the center of the slide.

- Using absorbent paper, gently remove the excess liquid from the corners. Do not touch the slides.

- Add at least one drop of fluorescence mounting medium per each slide. Place the coverslip, avoiding creating bubbles.

- Allow the slides to dry for 30 min and seal the borders with nail polish. Wait until the next day for microscope analysis. Keep the samples in the dark at 4°C.

Working Solutions

BLOCKING SOLUTION	WASH SOLUTION	ANTIBODY SOLUTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triton X-100 at 0.5% final concentration • Fish gelatin at 5% final concentration • Use PBS 1X (pH 7.4) to complete the desired volume 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triton X-100 at 0.1% final concentration dissolved in PBS 1X (pH 7.4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Triton X-100 at 0.2% final concentration dissolved in PBS 1X (pH 7.4)

Primary Antibodies against PGP9.5 (choose between them according to the combination with other primary antibodies)

Antibody	Recommended dilution	Manufacturer	Ref Code	Clonality	Storage
PGP 9.5	1:1000	Zytomed Systems	516-3344	Rabbit, polyclonal	aliquots -20°C
PGP 9.5	1:2000	Invitrogen	480012	Mouse, monoclonal	aliquots -20°C

Secondary Antibodies

Antibody	Recommended dilution	Manufacturer	Ref Code	Host and Specificity	Storage
Cyanine Cy™3	1:500	Jackson	711-167-003	Donkey Anti-Rabbit	aliquots -20°C
Alexa Fluor 594	1:500	Invitrogen	A-21203	Goat Anti-Mouse	4°C

Mounting Medium: Vectashield ® HardSet™ (with DAPI, Cat N° H-1500-10, Vector Laboratories).